

BIOLOGICAL SCIENCES

REGARDING THE MECHANISMS OF ACTION OF ALIPHATIC HYDROCARBONS ON THE ANIMAL REPRODUCTIVE SYSTEM

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Abstract

Medical and biological studies are currently of particular relevance to the impact of various man-made pollutants, such as aliphatic hydrocarbons on the human body. Aliphatic hydrocarbons are the most frequently encountered hydrocarbons known to humans. Therefore, poisoning by these products is often caused by solvents. Inhalation addiction to adhesives is also related to an addictive state formed by the action of organic solvents on the CNS. Literature review on the nature of hexane's effects on the body indicates that although there is a large range of data on the effects of hexane on the body, it has not been sufficiently investigated. There is much data on the effects of hexane on the nervous system. Hexane is also known to affect lung tissue. Toxicants can cause adverse effects at any stage of the function. The adverse effects of toxicants (and their metabolites) on male and female reproductive organs may be due to either disruption of the mechanisms of physiological regulation of their functions or to direct cytotoxic effects. Both laboratory and epidemiological studies have found that many xenobiotics have a fairly high potential for reproductive toxicity. Sensitivity to a particular teratogen varies considerably among representatives of different species, subspecies and even individuals of the same species. It follows that the significance is not so much the mechanism of action of the toxicant as the fact that the cellular elements are damaged at a certain stage of development of the organism, initiating a largely identical sequence of events leading to deformities.

Keywords: hydrocarbon, animal, hexane, reproductive function, mechanism

Aliphatic hydrocarbons are the most frequently encountered hydrocarbons known to humans. It is due to the fact that the main component of oil are alkanes [1]. Aromatic hydrocarbons have a better solvent capacity compared to gasoline, but they are highly toxic and therefore rarely used in domestic industry [2]. All organic solvents are characterized by similar toxicological properties: they inhibit central nervous system functions (narcotic effect). As a rule, solvents are a mixture of compounds and include nitrogen and sulphur compounds, as well as petrol and some oils. They are used in the manufacture of dyes, varnishes, adhesives etc. Therefore, poisoning by these products is often caused by solvents [3]. Inhalation addiction to adhesives is also related to an addictive state formed by the action of organic solvents on the CNS [4-5].

Hexane is widely used as a solvent in the production of synthetic materials (polyethylene, polypropylene, etc.), commonly mixed with other solvents and toluene. Hexane is widely used as a solvent in the tyre industry, in adhesives for the shoe industry, for the extraction of vegetable oils, in the textile, leather and furniture industries. Various grades of gasoline also have significant hexane content.

Literature review on the nature of hexane's effects on the body indicates that although there is a large range of data on the effects of hexane on the body, it has not been sufficiently investigated [6-8]. There is much data on the effects of hexane on the nervous system. There are cases of polyneuritis, loss of color vision, etc. In experiments on animals the effects on various enzyme systems in lungs were observed in the form of atelectasis and edema of lungs, changes in monooxygenase system of liver, atrophic changes in thymus and spleen, disorders of lymph nodes [9-12] were noted. Particularly, the impact on the nervous system inevitably leads to disorders of the digestive system: reduced intestinal peristalsis, changes in the integrity of enterocytes of the small and large intestine, impaired synthesis of digestive enzymes. Disorders of the pancreas and liver are to be expected naturally. Hexane is also known to affect lung tissue [13]. However, there is no data on the effect of hexane on the reproductive system of animals. Meanwhile, the indicators of these systems may be important features characterizing the threshold of hexane action.

Reproductive function is carried out as a complex sequence of physiological processes in mammals. Toxicants can cause adverse effects at any stage of the function. The complexity of the reproduction phenomenon makes it highly vulnerable to both xenobiotics and aliphatic hydrocarbons. What makes the phenomenon difficult to understand is that reproductive disorders can be the consequence of even acute toxic effects on various organs and systems of one of the "participants" in the process, at different periods, and manifest only after many months and sometimes years, defects in conception, nurturance, fetal development and the failure of the growing organism [14-16]. It is sometimes almost impossible to identify the exact mechanism underlying reproductive disorders, as the eco-toxicants can affect either both parents, only one of them, or the mother and fetus. The adverse effects of toxicants (and their metabolites) on male and female reproductive organs may be due to either disruption of the mechanisms of physiological regulation of their functions or to direct cytotoxic effects [17]. The disturbance of hormonal regulation of ovarian function may result from the competition of xenobiotics with sex hormones (androgens, contraceptives), action on estrogen receptors (organochlorine and organophosphorus compounds), changes in production rate. Postnatal reproductive performance can be affected by xenobiotics ingested by the breastfeeding mother and excreted with breast milk. Substances such as metals (mercury, lead), tetrachloroethane, halogenated aromatic hydrocarbons (dibenzofurans, biphenyls, dioxides), pesticides (DDT, dieldrin, heptachlor, etc.) can enter the neonate this way in large amounts [18]. In reproductive disorders, polygenic (action on various organs and systems), multifactorial (action of several toxicants), and synergistic (unidirectional spontaneous and toxicant-induced developmental disorders) effects are the most common. The main manifestations of the toxic effects of chemicals on the organs and tissues responsible for reproductive functions of the body and directly on the fetus are: infertility and teratogenesis. Teratogenic is the action of a chemical substance on the body of the mother, father or fetus, accompanied by a significant increase in the likelihood of structural and functional disorders in offspring. Substances with teratogenic activity are called teratogens. It is believed that almost any chemical substance introduced into the body of the father or mother, at some time in pregnancy in a large enough dose can cause teratogenesis. For this reason, only toxicants in the narrow sense should be referred to as teratogens, causing effects in concentrations that have no discernible effect on the parental organism. Both laboratory and epidemiological studies have found that many xenobiotics have a fairly high potential for reproductive toxicity. About 40% of the approximately three thousand xenobiotics surveyed have teratogenic properties. Sensitivity to a particular teratogen varies considerably among representatives of different species, subspecies and even individuals of the same species. Rabbits and mice, for example, are very sensitive to cortisone, which causes cleft palate in offspring. Rats do not show this defect when exposed to the substance. Humans, higher pri-

mates and some albino rabbit lines are extremely sensitive to the teratogenic action of thalidomide; individual rat and mouse lines only respond to very high doses of the substance. Most mammals are resistant to the toxicant. Different substances with different mechanisms of toxicity, when acting on the fetus during the same critical period, often cause the same types of disorders. It follows that the significance is not so much the mechanism of action of the toxicant as the fact that the cellular elements are damaged at a certain stage of development of the organism, initiating a largely identical sequence of events leading to deformities.

Theoretically, the risk of reproductive dysfunction can only be assessed in terms of xenobiotic doses since, as mentioned above, there are virtually no substances that are safe under any exposure conditions and in any doses. However, in practice, it is currently not possible to do this for humans. An extremely complex methodology for obtaining data to develop dose-response relationships, as applied to the problem in question, does not allow us to accumulate the necessary information.

Therefore, there is undoubted interest in studying the reproductive performance of experimental animals exposed to aliphatic hydrocarbons, particularly hexane, the work carried out will make it possible to study the dynamics of development of changes in intoxication in more detail.

REFERENCES:

1. Adeeva V., Liu H.Y., Xu B.Q., Sachtler W.M. Alkane isomerization over sulfated zirconia and other solid acids // *Topics in Catalysis*, 1998. - № 6(1). - pp. 61-76.
2. Matsushashi H., Shibata H., Nakamura H., Arata K. Skeletal isomerization mechanism of alkanes over solid superacid of sulfated zirconia // *Applied Catalysis A: General*, 1999. - № 187(1). - pp. 99-106.
3. Yamaguchi T. Alkane isomerization and acidity assessment on sulfated ZrO₂ // *Applied Catalysis A: General*, 2001. - № 222(1-2). pp. 237-246.
4. Jiménez C., Romero F.J., Roldán R., Marinas J.M., Gómez J.P. (2003) Hydroisomerization of a hydrocarbon feed containing n-hexane, n-heptane and cyclohexane on zeolite-supported platinum catalysts // *Applied Catalysis A: General*, 2003. - № 249(1). - pp. 175-185.
5. Liu H., Lei G.D., Sachtler W.M. Alkane isomerization over solid acid catalysts Effects of one-dimensional micropores // *Applied Catalysis A: General*, 1996. - № 137(1). - pp. 167-177.
6. Jao R.M., Leu L.J., Chang J.R. Effects of catalyst preparation and pretreatment on light naphtha isomerization over mordenite-supported Pt catalysts: optimal reduction temperature for pure feed and for sulfur-containing feed // *Applied Catalysis A: General*, 1996. - № 135(2). - pp. 301-316.
7. Chao K.J., Wu H.C., Leu L.J. Hydroisomerization of light normal paraffins over series of platinum-loaded mordenite and beta catalysts // *Applied Catalysis A: General*, 1996. - № 143(2). - pp. 223-243.
8. Holló A., Hancsok J., Kalló D. Kinetics of hydroisomerization of C₅-C₇ alkanes and their

mixtures over platinum containing mordenite // *Applied Catalysis A: General*, 2002. - № 229(1-2). - pp. 93-102.

9. Chao K.J., Lin C.C., Lin C.H., Wu H.C., Tseng C.W., Chen S.H. n-Heptane hydroconversion on platinum-loaded mordenite and beta zeolites: the effect of reaction pressure // *Applied Catalysis A: General*, 2000. - № 203(2). - pp. 211-220.

10. De Lucas A., Ramos M.J., Dorado F., Sánchez P., Valverde J.L. Influence of the Si/Al ratio in the hydroisomerization of n-octane over platinum and palladium beta zeolite-based catalysts with or without binder // *Applied Catalysis A: General*, 2005. - № 289(2). - pp. 205-213.

11. Blomsma E., Martens J.A., Jacobs P.A. Mechanisms of heptane isomerization on bifunctional Pd/H-Beta zeolites // *Journal of catalysis*, 1996. - № 159(2). - pp. 323-331.

12. Blomsma E., Martens J.A., Jacobs P.A. Isomerization and hydrocracking of heptane over bimetallic bifunctional PtPd/H-beta and PtPd/USY zeolite catalysts // *Journal of Catalysis*, 1997. - № 165(2). - pp. 241-248.

13. Remy M.J., Stanica D., Poncelet G., Feijen J.P., Grobet P.J., Martens J.A., Jacobs P.A. Dealuminated H- Y zeolites: relation between

physicochemical properties and catalytic activity in heptane and decane isomerization // *The Journal of Physical Chemistry*, 1996. - № 100(30). - pp. 12440-12447.

14. Pope T.D., Kriz J.F., Stanciulescu M., Monnier J. A study of catalyst formulations for isomerization of C7 hydrocarbons // *Applied Catalysis A: General*, 2002. - № 233(1-2). - pp. 45-62.

15. Stöcker M. Gas phase catalysis by zeolites // *Microporous and Mesoporous Materials*, 2005. - № 82(3). - pp. 257-292.

16. Abramova A.V., Slivinskii E.V., Skryleva E.A. Study of the structure and composition of decationated dealuminated Y zeolites // *Kinetics and catalysis*, 1998. - № 39(3). - pp. 421-429.

17. Yushchenko V.V. (1997) Calculation of the acidity spectra of catalysts from temperature-programmed ammonia desorption data // *Russian Journal of Physical Chemistry A*, 1997. - № 71(4). - pp. 547-550.

18. Kitaev L.E., Bukina Z.M., Yushchenko V.V., Abramova A.V., Slivinskii E.V. Modification of acid properties and catalytic activity of ultrastable zeolite Y treated with aqueous solutions of boric and phosphoric acids // *Petroleum Chemistry*, 2003. - № 43(3). - pp. 159-166.